

Kinetic Studies of the Oxidation of Fructose by Ammoniacal Silver Nitrate

Awant P. Modi and Satyeshwar Ghosh

The measurement of the kinetics of the reduction of silver in ammoniacal solution leads to the conclusion that the rate of reaction is first order with respect to silver nitrate but has a tendency to increase at a lower temperature or decreasing ammonia concentration. Fructose concentration has hardly any effect on reaction rate at a higher temperature but the order is found to be fractional at low temperatures. The rate constants, calculated after the expiry of induction period, decrease with increasing concentration of ammonia. The average values of temperature coefficient for 10° rise, energy and entropy of activation are 4.10, 25.80 k.cals./mole and 8 962 e.u. respectively.

The mechanism of oxidation of fructose by ammoniacal silver nitrate is suggested through the enolic transformation of the carbonyl group. The determination of the number of equivalents of silver consumed per mole of monosaccharose shows that the molecule undergoes a fission to yield glycollic and oxalic acids as oxidised products.

A search of literature shows that the kinetics of the reaction between ammoniacal silver nitrate and fructose has been almost neglected. The reaction appeared interesting, particularly because of the presence of ketonic group in fructose molecule. Ammoniacal silver nitrate solutions are reduced by aldehydes and hydroxy acid like tartaric, and has been described as a reagent for quantitative estimation of an aldehydic compound. The present investigation is therefore undertaken to elucidate kinetics and mechanism of the reduction of ammoniacal silver nitrate by fructose.

All the chemicals used were of extra pure quality and the solutions were prepared in fresh double distilled water. The experimental technique adopted is the same as described in an earlier publication¹. The rate constants were determined after the expiry of the induction period, and it is found that the order of reaction with respect to silver in solution decreases from two to one with the increasing concentration of ammonia. Furthermore, the reaction follows first order law satisfactorily when temperature is raised to 35° in the presence of even 0.0416*M* ammonia as will be seen from Table I.

TABLE I

Fructose—0.0750*M* Silver Nitrate—0.020*M*

Temperature—35°

Concentrations of ammonia	0.0416 <i>M</i>	0.0624 <i>M</i>	0.0832 <i>M</i>
$K_1 \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	87.2	27.11	12.83

1. A. P. Modi and S. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 446.

Effect of Fructose Concentration : The effect on reaction velocity was studied by varying the initial concentration of fructose and keeping the concentration of silver nitrate same in the reaction mixture. The Table II shows that the reaction rates slightly decrease with the decrease of fructose concentrations, but at a higher temperature 35° (Table III), the rate constants tend to become independent of fructose concentration.

TABLE II

Silver Nitrate = 0.020*M*; Ammonium Hydroxide = 0.0624*M*

Temperature = 25°

Fructose concentrations	0.050 <i>M</i>	0.0750 <i>M</i>	0.150 <i>M</i>
$K_1 \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	4.356	5.351	6.665

TABLE III

Silver Nitrate = 0.020*M* Ammonium Hydroxide = 0.0832*M*

Temperature = 35°

Fructose concentrations	0.050 <i>M</i>	0.0750 <i>M</i>	0.150 <i>M</i>
$K_1 \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	10.43	12.83	12.99

Thus the order of the reaction between fructose and ammoniacal silver nitrate above 35° is one.

Effect of Ammonia on Rate Constants : An increase in concentration of ammonia decreases the reaction velocity and an induction period is marked. The value of induction period decreases with the increase in temperature as noted in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Silver Nitrate = 0.020*M*Fructose = 0.150*M*

Concentra- tions of Ammonia	$K_1 \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹) at 35°	Time in minutes for induction period		
		at 25°	at 30°	at 35°
0.0416 <i>M</i>	89.54	—	3	2
0.0624 <i>M</i>	27.41	40	5	5
0.0832 <i>M</i>	12.99	—	30	10
0.1248 <i>M</i>	7.130	—	—	20

Temperature Coefficient : The temperature coefficient for 10° rise (25°–35°), calculated from the average values of first order constants of 0.150*M* fructose in the presence of 0.0624*M* ammonia, is found to be 4.10.

Energy and Entropy of Activation : The energy of activation from the average first order rate constants of two different temperatures and the entropy of activation are also calculated and the values are found to be 25.8 k.cals. per mole and 8.962 e.u. respectively.

Determination of Equivalents : The equivalents of silver nitrate for the oxidation of a mole of fructose were determined by the same procedure that is given in the case of glucose², and the average value of three experiments is found to be nearly 10.0 equivalents. This suggests the formation of glycollic and oxalic acids. It is to be noted here that these compounds are not oxidisable by ammoniacal silver nitrate at the conditions of the experiment.

DISCUSSION

The determination of equivalents consumed per mole of fructose shows that a C-C fission occurs in order to yield glycollic and oxalic acids as oxidised products. Fructose is a polyol ketone and a ketonic group is well known to undergo enolisation in acid medium. The process involves the attachment of a proton and subsequently its removal by a base schematically :

The stronger the attachment of proton smaller will be the acid concentration to effect step (1) of enolisation and higher concentration of a base will be required for its removal (step-2) A carbonyl group attached with—CH₂OH group requires smaller concentration of H⁺ ion for the first process and greater concentration of OH⁻ for its removal.

We have suggested a mechanism in the case of glucose² which also involves the oxidation of the molecule through enolic transformation of the carbonyl group yielding corresponding carboxylic acid. Similar steps may be explained in the case of fructose as the products obtained in step (2) are aldehydes. These aldehydes will yield erythronic and glycollic acids. The former is a hydroxy acid and we have seen that the oxidation of a hydroxy acid like tartaric is through the formation of a co-ordinated complex with free silver ion, therefore, similar coordination is possible in this case also. Thus :

Erythronic Acid

These aldehydes will give oxalic and glycollic acids.

The kinetic studies of this reaction reveals that there is an induction period in the early stages of the reaction. This may be explained taking into consideration of the early steps of enolisation. The step (2) requires a larger concentration of ammonia in order to remove a proton, and if the concentration of ammonia is increased, a large quantity of silver forms the argento-ammines, $\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)^+$ and $\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)_2^+$, decreasing the concentration of free silver ions. Moreover, the free silver ions are required for the formation of coordinated complex with hydroxy acid. Therefore, with decreasing the concentration of ammonia the induction period decreases.

The data collected show that the order of the reaction with respect to silver in solution is two at a lower temperature when low concentration of ammonia is used. This may be explained because of the step (4) which becomes the rate determining one. At higher temperature, it appears that step (5) becomes prominent and it is the rate determining step.